

LOCALIZED CURRICULUM ON LEARNERS' ENGAGEMENT IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION PROGRAM

Jeselle P. Cecilio, LPT ¹, Consuelo R. Saenz, EdD ²

¹ *Mabini Colleges, Incorporated, Daet, Camarines Norte, Philippines*

² *Camarines Norte State College, Daet, Camarines Norte, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the influence of a localized curriculum on engagement levels of students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) within inclusive education settings in Bicol-speaking schools under DepEd Camarines Norte for the academic year 2023–2024. Utilizing a quantitative methodology and a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 62 teachers via surveys. The analysis employed a weighted mean and Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation to examine the relationship between the components of the localized curriculum and student engagement. The results revealed that students with SEN demonstrated high levels of engagement when exposed to the localized curriculum, with all components receiving strong agreement from the participating teachers. Notable correlations were identified between curriculum adaptation and flexibility and learners' engagement levels across various areas: content, teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, and localized learning materials. Furthermore, a strong statistical significance was observed between the quality and diversity of teaching staff and engagement in content, teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, and localized learning materials. A primary challenge identified in implementing a localized curriculum was the need to adapt the curriculum to cater to the varied needs of SEN learners. To address this challenge, the study proposes an intervention program titled FOR ALL (Facilitating Opportunities and Resources for Accessible Localized Learning): A Workshop Series and Materials Localization for Inclusive Education.

Keywords: *Localized curriculum, learner engagement, Inclusive Education Program, Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), content of the localized curriculum,*

teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, localized learning materials, curriculum adaptation and flexibility, quality and diverse teachers, school policies and practices, safe and supportive environment, assessment and feedback

INTRODUCTION

The concept of inclusive education, rooted in international law and principles, has evolved to promote equal educational opportunities for all learners, irrespective of their abilities (Abdullajonova, 2022). However, Nilholm (2020) research highlights persistent challenges and limited progress in inclusive education despite extensive studies, emphasizing the need for a critical examination of its theoretical foundations and the development of effective improvement theories. Localized curriculum, as emphasized by various studies (Taherizade and Shabany, 2019; Olivier, 2020; Baghbanian et al., 2020), is a crucial educational approach tailored to address the specific needs of regions or student groups.

Interviews with SPED teachers in DepEd Camarines Norte offer valuable insights into inclusive education practices, revealing that children undergo preparatory phases in non-graded classes before integration into the inclusive education program. They also mentioned that one of the challenges in working with learners with special educational needs is the difficulty in capturing their attention and engagement during class. The curriculum for these children aligns closely with regular classes, with a focus on customization to cater to division needs and contribute to achieving SDG 4. Notably, DepEd Camarines Norte provided training for writers to craft detailed lesson plans and localize content in line with legislative frameworks established by Republic Act RA 11650 and guided by RA 10533 section 5.

While existing studies provide valuable insights into inclusive education and localized curriculum, they do not directly address the research gap concerning engagement levels of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) as beneficiaries of the localized curriculum in DepEd Camarines Norte. The study was then conducted to determine the influence of localized curriculum on learners' engagement in an inclusive education program. The result of this study was used as a basis for the proposed intervention to increase the level of engagement of learners in the Inclusive Education Program.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the influence of the localized curriculum on engagement levels of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education programs within Bicol-speaking schools in DepEd Camarines Norte SY 2023-2024. Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of engagement in the localized curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) under the DepEd inclusive education program as perceived by their teachers in terms of:

- 1.1 content of the localized curriculum;
 - 1.2 teaching and learning activities;
 - 1.3 assessment tasks; and
 - 1.4 localized learning materials?
2. What are the specific components of the localized curriculum that contribute significantly to the engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education settings in terms of:
- 2.1 curriculum adaptation and flexibility;
 - 2.2 quality and diverse teachers;
 - 2.3 school policies and practices;
 - 2.4 safe and supportive environment; and
 - 2.5 assessment and feedback?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of engagement in the localized curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) and the specific components of the localized curriculum that contribute significantly to their engagement?
4. What challenges were encountered during the implementation of the localized curriculum in the Inclusive Education Program?
5. Based on the study's findings, what intervention may be proposed to increase the level of engagement of learners in the Inclusive Education Program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a quantitative research method using a descriptive-correlation research design. Descriptive study was used by the researchers to describe the phenomenon being studied. It determined the level of engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education implementing localized curriculum.

In addition, correlational research design was utilized to examine if there is a significant relationship between localized curriculum and the engagement level of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education program. The study's goal is to gather and examine data in order to find significant relationship between the level of engagement and the specific components of the localized curriculum that contribute significantly to the engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education. Thus, a descriptive-correlation design was deemed appropriate for this study.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This study employed a quantitative research method using a descriptive-correlation research design. It utilized total enumeration sampling technique that includes all 65 teachers responsible for learners with special needs actively enrolled in the inclusive education program within the Bicol-speaking schools in DepEd Camarines Norte. However, a total of 62 teachers participated in this study. Three teachers declined to participate, which is within their rights as mentioned in the ethical standards.

Description of the Respondents

The eight schools in Bicol Speaking Schools within the Division of Camarines Norte were chosen for this research. Within these schools that offer an inclusive education program, the research involved 62 teachers who work directly with learners having special educational needs. The selected schools represent the diversity and complexity of schools offering inclusive education in DepEd Camarines Norte, wherein various characteristics of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) are accommodated, and localized curriculum practices are implemented.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers first sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Schools Division Office of Camarines Norte to survey 65 teachers of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) enrolled in a specific school within Bicol speaking Schools in the Division of Camarines Norte.

Then, the researchers sought permission from the respondents to survey with an informed consent form. Out of 65 teachers, only 62 participated in this study. Three teachers declined to participate, which is within their rights as outlined in the ethical standards. The respondents' information was kept confidential. Before the tabulation of data, each name was replaced with a respondent number to maintain anonymity. Moreover, the research upholds gender and cultural sensitivity, treating all participants with the utmost respect of their diverse perspectives.

Research Instrument

A quantitative survey questionnaire was used as a research instrument. The questionnaire was researchers-made to suit the specific objectives of this study. To ensure the content validity of the questionnaire, experts in the field validated it including the Education Program Supervisor in SPED and two SPED School Coordinator. Also, pilot testing was conducted to evaluate the reliability of the research instrument. The results of the dry run obtained Cronbach's alpha to measure the internal consistency of the items, ensuring that they consistently measure the intended constructs.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The initial step involved descriptive statistical methods, such as the computation of the weighted mean and frequency count, to summarize the levels of engagement and perceptions of the influence of the localized curriculum in SOP number 1; to identify the specific components of the localized curriculum that are significantly contribute to the learners' engagement in inclusive education program mentioned in the SOP number 2; and to summarize the occurrence of each identified challenge in SOP number 4. This will provide a clear picture of the most common challenges encountered by teachers in implementing the localized curriculum. Using correlation, such as presenting a clear overview of the collected data in SOP number 3, which includes testing the hypothesis to determine the significant relationship of variables considered this study tested the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the localized curriculum and learners' engagement using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r).

The study sought to determine the influence of a localized curriculum on the engagement levels of these learners. It assessed the extent of engagement experienced by these learners concerning the localized curriculum within the Bicol speaking schools in DepEd inclusive education program. To accomplish the objectives, quantitative research methods using a descriptive-correlation design with structured questionnaires were employed. To answer the research questions, a researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather the level of engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) and to determine whether there is a significant relationship between localized curriculum and the engagement level of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). It was also used to identify the challenges encountered in implementing localized curriculum in inclusive education programs.

The limitation of the study was that it did not fully capture the personal and detailed experiences behind the numerical data. Additionally, the study primarily focused on how the localized curriculum influenced the engagement of learners with special educational needs in an inclusive classroom, without examining other potential factors that might also affect their level of engagement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Engagement in the Localized Curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) under the DepEd Inclusive Education Program. This study evaluates how a localized curriculum affects the engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) within the inclusive education program within Bicol-speaking schools in DepEd Camarines Norte SY 2023-2024. The analysis focuses on four domains: content, teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, and localized learning materials.

Content of the Localized Curriculum. The findings shown that an overall weighted mean of 3.35 indicates that learners are generally "Highly Engaged" with the content

provided in the localized curriculum. The results further show that the highest engagement was observed in indicator 3 (The content aligns with individual interests and preferences of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) with a weighted mean of 3.56 interpreted as “Highly Engaged,” while indicator 5 (The content fosters collaboration and interaction between peers to enhance social and emotional growth among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) got the lowest engagement with a weighted mean of 3.19 interpreted as “Moderately Engaged.”

The data indicate that Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) find the content of the localized curriculum engaging, particularly when it aligns with their interests and preferences. This alignment likely fosters a sense of relevance and connection to their learning experiences, contributing to higher engagement levels. In contrast, the lower engagement regarding collaboration and peer interaction suggests a need for more structured opportunities for social engagement in the curriculum, which may further enhance social and emotional development among learners.

Table 1

Level of Engagement in the Localized Curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) Along its Content

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The content uses auditory, visual, kinesthetic, and tactile modalities.	3.24	ME
2. The content includes culturally relevant content that reflects the background and experiences of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.32	HE
3. The content aligns with individual interests and preferences of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.56	HE
4. The content is linked to real-world contexts and applications relevant to the lives and interest of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.44	HE
5. The content fosters collaboration and interaction between peers to enhance social and emotional growth among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.19	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.35	HE
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00	-	Highly Engaged (HE)
2.50 – 3.24	-	Moderately Engaged (ME)
1.75 – 2.49	-	Engaged (E)
1.00 – 1.74	-	Not Engaged (NE)

The findings were corroborated by Francisco et al. (2020), who emphasize the benefits of tailored pedagogical strategies in fostering equitable learning environments for SEN students. Their work underscores how adapting content to the learners' contexts enhances both engagement and inclusivity, which is evident in the current study's high engagement ratings for culturally relevant and interest-aligned content. Similarly, Suguitan and Natividad (2022) conform to these findings by demonstrating that localized, game-based learning activities significantly improve student engagement and motivation, particularly through real-world applications and interactive materials.

Teaching and Learning Activities. As shown in table 2, the overall weighted mean of 3.46 interpreted as "Highly Engaged," shows that the localized curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) are highly engaged with the teaching and learning activities. The results further show that the highest engagement was observed in indicator 3 (Incorporation of multi-sensory materials, activities, and experiences) with a weighted mean of 3.79 interpreted as "Highly Engaged," while indicator 5 (Integration of technology tools e.g. educational apps and software) got the lowest engagement with a weighted mean of 3.21 interpreted as "Moderately Engaged."

The data reveal that activities catering to multiple senses effectively enhance engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). Higher engagement with multi-sensory materials suggests they stimulate cognitive and sensory functions crucial for SEN learners. Conversely, the moderate engagement in technology integration indicates that while technology is valuable, its use may need to be more aligned with the learning needs and preferences of these learners. The findings were supported by Rubtsov and Konokotin (2020), who highlight the developmental benefits of multi-sensory and interactive learning approaches in fostering cognitive and sensory functions among SEN students. Their research aligns with the current study's findings that multi-sensory materials are particularly engaging for SEN learners. Additionally, Vidal et al. (2022) conform to these findings by demonstrating interactive tools and differentiated instructional strategies, such as using digital classroom tools, enhance engagement and accommodate diverse learner needs.

Table 2

Level of Engagement in the Localized Curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) Along Teaching and Learning Activities

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Use of graphic organizers and visual representations	3.23	ME
2. Use of hands-on interactive learning activities	3.53	HE
3. Incorporation of multi-sensory materials, activities, and experiences	3.79	HE
4. Use of differentiated learning tasks	3.55	HE
5. Integration of technology tools e.g. educational apps and software	3.21	ME
Overall Weighted Mean	3.46	HE
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00		- Highly Engaged (HE)
2.50 – 3.24		- Moderately Engaged (ME)
1.75 – 2.49		- Engaged (E)
1.00 – 1.74		- Not Engaged (NE)

Assessment Tasks. As shown in table 3, the overall weighted mean of 3.26 indicates that learners are generally "Highly Engaged" with the assessment tasks. The results further show that the highest engagement was found in indicator 1 (Hands-on project-based assessment related to real-world scenarios) with a weighted mean of 3.47 interpreted as "Highly Engaged," while indicator 3 (Storytelling performances of the local legends, myths, and folktales passed down through generations) received the lowest engagement score with a weighted mean of 2.98 interpreted as "Moderately Engaged." The data indicate that Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) are more engaged when assessment tasks are practical and linked to real-life situations. The higher engagement in hands-on, project-based assessments suggests that these tasks provide meaningful context for learners. Conversely, storytelling performances may not effectively engage all learners, possibly due to challenges in oral communication or personal interest. This indicates a need for differentiated approaches in assessment methods that accommodate diverse expressive abilities. The findings were corroborated by Taherizade and Shabany (2019), who emphasize the importance of localized curricula and practical tasks in enhancing engagement and learning outcomes for diverse learners. Their work supports the idea that culturally and contextually relevant assessments stimulate interest and participation. Similarly, Tolentino et al. (2020) conform to these findings by showcasing the effectiveness of localized digital learning modules that integrate cultural and real-world contexts, significantly improving learner engagement in assessment tasks.

Table 3

Level of Engagement in the Localized Curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) Along Assessment Tasks

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Hands-on project-based assessment related to real-world scenarios	3.47	HE
2. Role playing, simulation, or presentation to demonstrate their skills	3.23	ME
3. Storytelling performances of the local legends, myths, and folktales passed down through generations	2.98	ME
4. Showcase the diversity of cultural expressions through artworks	3.34	HE
5. Cultural performances that reflect their heritage and identity	3.26	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	HE

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	- Highly Engaged (HE)
2.50 – 3.24	- Moderately Engaged (ME)
1.75 – 2.49	- Engaged (E)
1.00 – 1.74	- Not Engaged (NE)

Localized Learning Materials. As shown in table 4, the overall weighted mean of 3.51 indicates that learners are generally "Highly Engaged" with the localized learning

materials. The results further show that the highest engagement was recorded for indicator 2 (Local songs and musical instruments) with a weighted mean of 3.66 interpreted as “Highly Engaged,” while indicator 3 (Stories written by local authors) scored slightly lower with a weighted mean of 3.40 interpreted as “Highly Engaged.”

Table 4

Level of Engagement in the Localized Curriculum of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) Along Localized Learning Materials

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Local artworks and crafts	3.47	HE
2. Local songs and musical instruments	3.66	HE
3. Stories written by local authors (folktales, legends etc.)	3.40	HE
4. Samples of local specimens -plants, animals, rocks, etc.	3.52	HE
5. Maps of local geography	3.48	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	HE
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00	-	Highly Engaged (HE)
2.50 – 3.24	-	Moderately Engaged (ME)
1.75 – 2.49	-	Engaged (E)
1.00 – 1.74	-	Not Engaged (NE)

The findings suggest that incorporating culturally relevant materials like local music effectively captures the interest of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The high engagement with musical elements could be attributed to the auditory appeal and cultural connection. While local stories engage students, the slightly lower engagement may indicate a need for more interactive storytelling techniques or adaptations to meet diverse learning needs. Thus, teachers may explore various formats for presenting local stories to further enhance engagement. The findings were supported by Gutierrez and Pascual (2022), who highlights the benefits of integrating localized and contextualized teaching strategies, particularly those emphasizing cultural elements like local music and artifacts, to improve engagement and learning outcomes. Similarly, Khotimah and Sutarto (2020) conform to these findings by demonstrating the positive effects of using culturally relevant materials in inclusive education, where local stories, songs, and artifacts play a significant role in fostering a deeper connection between learners and their curriculum.

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). This study examines the specific components of a localized curriculum that contribute to the engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in inclusive education programs within Bicol-speaking schools in DepEd Camarines Norte for SY 2023-2024. The evaluation emphasizes five key areas: curriculum adaptation and flexibility, quality and diverse teachers, school policies and practices, a safe and supportive environment, and assessment and feedback.

Curriculum Adaptation and Flexibility. As shown in table 5, the overall weighted mean of 3.66 indicates that the respondents generally "Strongly Agree" with the components related to curriculum adaptation and flexibility. The highest score was recorded for indicator 3 which is on modification of lesson plans and activities with a weighted mean of 3.79 interpreted as "Strongly Agree," while indicator 5 (Inclusive contents that reflect the diverse background of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) received the lowest score with a weighted mean of 3.48 interpreted as "Strongly Agree."

The data suggest that Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) benefit significantly from a curriculum that is adaptable and flexible. The high engagement observed in the modification of lesson plans and activities indicates that personalized approaches enhance learner interest and involvement. However, the relatively lower engagement in inclusive content reflects the ongoing need to ensure that all curricular materials genuinely represent the diverse backgrounds of learners. This highlights the importance of continuous evaluation and adaptation of the curriculum to maximize engagement for all Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The findings were corroborated by Francisco et al. (2020), who emphasize the role of tailored curricular adaptations and inclusive practices in fostering equitable learning environments. Their research supports the findings that localized and modified materials, lesson plans, and assessments are pivotal in meeting the unique needs of SEN learners. Similarly, Kefallinou et al. (2020) conform to these findings by advocating for the inclusion of diverse and adaptive curricular components that reflect the backgrounds and needs of all learners.

Table 5

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) along Curriculum Adaptation and Flexibility

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Localization of learning objectives and experiences to meet the unique needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.76	SA
2. Modification of learning materials and assessment methods	3.69	SA
3. Modification of lesson plans and activities	3.79	SA
4. Provision of adaptive materials, resources, and technologies such as modified textbooks, assistive devices, and audio-visual aids.	3.56	SA
5. Inclusive contents that reflect the diverse background of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)	3.48	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.66	SA
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00		- Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50 – 3.24		- Moderately Agree (MA)
1.75 – 2.49		- Agree (A)
1.00 – 1.74		- Disagree (D)

Quality and Diverse Teachers. As shown in table 6, the overall weighted mean of 3.31 indicates that the respondents generally answered "Strongly Agree" with the contributions of teachers in engaging Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The highest score was observed in indicator 2, which refers to teachers foster positive relationships with Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) with a weighted mean of 3.87 interpreted as strongly agree, while indicator 1 on teachers in inclusive education settings receive adequate training and professional development on catering to the needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) received the lowest score with a weighted mean of 2.47 interpreted as agree.

Table 6

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) along Quality and Diverse Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Teachers in inclusive education settings receive adequate training and professional development on catering to the needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	2.47	A
2. Teachers foster positive relationships with Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment.	3.87	SA
3. Teachers are skilled in developing and implementing localized lesson plans.	2.73	MA
4. Teachers collaborate with colleagues and specialists to support Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)	3.76	SA
5. Teachers demonstrate adaptability and flexibility in responding to the needs and challenges of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)	3.74	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.31	SA
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00	-	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50 – 3.24	-	Moderately Agree (MA)
1.75 – 2.49	-	Agree (A)
1.00 – 1.74	-	Disagree (D)

The findings imply that positive teacher-student relationships significantly enhance engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The high engagement in this area suggests that when teachers create supportive environments, learners feel more valued and involved. In contrast, the lower score for adequate training indicates a gap in teachers' preparedness to meet the specific needs of SEN learners, which may hinder their ability to provide the necessary support. This indicates that continuous professional development is essential for enhancing teachers' effectiveness in inclusive settings. The findings were supported by Pérez-Salas et al. (2021), who highlight the critical role of teacher-student relationships in fostering engagement and reducing disengagement among SEN learners. Their study confirms that supportive relationships are foundational for creating inclusive and engaging learning environments. Additionally, Boyle and Anderson (2020) conform to these findings by stressing the

necessity of teacher training and professional development in building inclusive education systems. However, the current study’s findings of low engagement in the area of teacher training suggests a persistent gap, which Boyle and Anderson also identify as a systemic barrier to achieving fully inclusive practices.

School Policies and Practices. As shown in table 7, the overall weighted mean of 3.85 indicates that the respondents generally "Strongly Agree" with the impact of school policies and practices on their engagement. The highest score was observed in indicator 2 (The school has clear steps for identifying and supporting Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).) with a weighted mean of 3.94 interpreted as “Strongly Agree,” while indicator 1 (The school has policies that include all learners and ensure equal access to education for those with special educational needs) received a slightly lower score with a weighted mean of 3.65 interpreted as “Strongly Agree.”

Table 7

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) along School Policies and Practices

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The school has policies that include all learners and ensure equal access to education for those with special educational needs (SEN).	3.65	SA
2. The school has clear steps for identifying and supporting Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.94	SA
3. The school encourages students and staff to respect and value diversity.	3.84	SA
4. The school works with parents, guardians, and caregivers to provide better support for Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.90	SA
5. The school ensures that classrooms and facilities are safe and accessible for Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.92	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.85	SA
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00		- Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50 – 3.24		- Moderately Agree (MA)
1.75 – 2.49		- Agree (A)
1.00 – 1.74		- Disagree (D)

The findings imply that well-defined guidelines and procedures are crucial for supporting Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), as reflected in the high engagement scores. This implies further that when schools implement clear frameworks for inclusion, learners feel more secured and engaged in their educational experiences. However, the slightly lower engagement concerning inclusion policies may indicate a need for ongoing evaluation and enhancement of these policies. The findings were supported by Shaeffer (2019), who emphasizes that inclusive education policies are prerequisites for equity and social justice, enabling SEN learners to access quality education in supportive environments. His work supports the idea that clearly defined inclusion frameworks significantly enhance student engagement and well-being. Similarly, Casinto (2022)

conforms to these findings by highlighting the role of school climate and instructional leadership in promoting inclusivity and respect for diversity, which aligns with the present study's high engagement scores related to respect for diversity and collaboration with families.

Safe and Supportive Environment. As shown in table 8, the overall weighted mean of 3.71 indicates that the respondents generally "Strongly Agree" with the elements of a safe and supportive environment contributing to their engagement. The highest score was recorded for indicator 4 (Faculty and staff are patient, understanding, and supportive when interacting with Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) with a weighted mean of 3.90 interpreted as "Strongly Agree," while indicator 2 (The school has quiet spaces where Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) can relax or calm down when needed) received a lower score of 3.47 interpreted as "Strongly Agree."

Table 8

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) along Safe and Supportive Environment

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. The school is accessible and designed to meet the physical and sensory needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.55	SA
2. The school has quiet spaces where Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) can relax or calm down when needed.	3.47	SA
3. Anti-bullying rules are enforced to protect Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.85	SA
4. Faculty and staff are patient, understanding, and supportive when interacting with Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.90	SA
5. The school offers counseling and programs to help Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) manage emotions and behavior.	3.79	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.71	SA
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00		- Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50 – 3.24		- Moderately Agree (MA)
1.75 – 2.49		- Agree (A)
1.00 – 1.74		- Disagree (D)

The findings indicate that safety and emotional well-being are paramount for engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The high score for supportive staff and faculty reflects the importance of a supportive school culture that prioritizes student well-being. However, the lower score for designated quiet spaces indicates a potential area for improvement, suggesting that not all learners may have adequate access to these resources. Thus, creating more sensory-friendly environments could further enhance engagement. The findings were corroborated by Rubtsov and Konokotin

(2020), who stress the importance of social and emotional support in creating inclusive spaces that foster cognitive and emotional development for SEN learners. Their work underscores how supportive interactions and environments improve student engagement and overall well-being. Similarly, Casinto (2022) conforms to these findings by highlighting the significance of a positive school climate, including anti-bullying measures and emotional support programs, in promoting inclusivity and engagement among diverse learners.

Assessment and Feedback. As shown in table 9, the overall weighted mean of 3.83 indicates that the respondents generally answered "Strongly Agree" with the role of assessment and feedback in their engagement. The highest score was recorded for indicator 2 (Teachers provide timely and constructive feedback to Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) with a weighted mean of 3.95 interpreted as "Strongly Agree," while indicator 3 (Assessment practices emphasize strengths-based approaches, highlighting the unique talents and capabilities of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs)) received a lower score of 3.73 interpreted as "Strongly Agree."

Table 9

Specific Components of the Localized Curriculum that Contribute to the Engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) Along Assessment and Feedback

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Assessment methods used in the curriculum are varied and flexible to accommodate the diverse needs and abilities of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.85	SA
2. Teachers provide timely and constructive feedback to Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), focusing on progress and areas for improvement.	3.95	SA
3. Assessment practices emphasize strengths-based approaches, highlighting the unique talents and capabilities of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.73	SA
4. Assessment practices incorporate formative assessment i.e. teacher observation and informal assessment to monitor progress of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).	3.76	SA
5. Feedback from Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) is valued and used to inform curriculum adaptations and instructional practices.	3.85	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.83	SA
<i>Rating Scale:</i>		<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
3.25 – 4.00		- Strongly Agree (SA)
2.50 – 3.24		- Moderately Agree (MA)
1.75 – 2.49		- Agree (A)
1.00 – 1.74		- Disagree (D)

The data reveal that timely and constructive feedback significantly enhances engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). The high engagement in this area suggests that when teachers provide specific feedback, learners feel more motivated and connected to their learning. The relatively lower score for strengths-based assessment practices indicates a potential area for growth, suggesting that emphasizing individual talents could further boost learner engagement. The findings were corroborated by Francisco et al. (2020), who highlight the importance of differentiated and strengths-based assessment practices in promoting equitable learning outcomes. Their research supports the findings that tailoring assessments to the unique needs and abilities of learners enhances both engagement and academic success. Similarly, Suguitan and Natividad (2022) conform to these findings by demonstrating that localized, game-based assessments incorporating real-world contexts and timely feedback foster higher motivation and active participation among learners.

Relationship between the Localized Curriculum in Inclusive Education Program of DepEd and the Learner’s Level of Engagement. It can be observed that the specific contents of the localized curriculum along curriculum adaptation and flexibility and the learner’s level of engagement in terms of content ($r=0.323$), teaching and learning activities ($r=0.322$), assessment tasks ($r=0.343$), and localized learning materials ($r=0.343$) while specific contents of the localized curriculum along quality and diverse teachers and the learner’s level of engagement in terms of content ($r=0.293$), teaching and learning activities($r=0.288$), assessment tasks ($r=0.485$), and localized learning materials ($r=0.378$) are all statistically significant at less than 0.05 and 0.01 significant levels ($p\text{-value}<.05$ and $p\text{-value}<.01$), indicating strong statistical significance.

Table 10

Test for Relationship Between the Localized Curriculum in Inclusive Program and the Learner’s Level of Engagement

Specific Contents	Level of Engagement of Learners							
	Content		Teaching and Learning Activity		Assessment Tasks		Localized Learning Materials	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Curriculum Adaptation and Flexibility	.323*	.010	.322*	.011	.343**	.006	.343**	.002
Quality and Diverse Teachers	.293*	.021	.288*	.023	.485**	.000	.378**	.002
Policies and Practices	.015	.910	-.071	.585	.006	.965	.030	.819
Supportive Environment	.032	.808	-.022	.866	-.051	.695	.042	.747
Assessment and Feedback	.162	.207	.147	.253	-.079	.543	.178	.167

*Correlation is significant @ 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant @ 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The results suggest that as the level of engagement along the variables considered increases, the specific components of the localized curriculum that contribute to the engagement of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) also tends to increase. It can be observed that both curriculum adaptation and flexibility and quality and diverse

teachers show a strong relationship with assessment tasks and localized learning materials. The findings were supported by Kefallinou et al. (2020), who emphasize that adaptable curricula and skilled teachers are essential for addressing diverse learner needs and fostering engagement. Their study supports the findings that flexible and customized instructional strategies directly impact learners' active participation and connection to the content. However, the present study's finding that policies, supportive environments, and assessment feedback do not significantly correlate with engagement refutes with Shaeffer (2019), who identifies these factors as critical to fostering equity and participation in inclusive education.

Challenges Encountered During the Implementation of Localized Curriculum in Inclusive Education Program. As shown in table 11, the most frequently encountered challenge is indicator 1 which refers to the difficulty in adapting the curriculum to address the diverse needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs), with a frequency of 58, ranked first.

Table 11

Challenges Encountered During the Implementation of Localized Curriculum in Inclusive Education Program

Indicators	Frequency	Rank
1. Difficulty in adapting the curriculum to address the diverse needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs).	58	1
2. Challenges in incorporating local culture, values, and knowledge effectively into the curriculum.	55	6.5
3. Insufficient training for teachers on the localized curriculum and inclusive education practices.	56	4
4. Inadequate school policies to support the implementation and sustainability of the localized curriculum.	23	10
5. Developing appropriate assessment tools that accurately reflect the localized curriculum objectives.	56	4
6. Creating a learning environment that supports the diverse backgrounds and needs of all students.	57	2
7. Addressing bullying and ensuring that all students feel valued and included.	54	8
8. Limited availability of localized teaching materials and resources such as assistive technologies and tools.	56	4
9. High teacher-pupil ratio makes it challenging to provide individualized attention and support for Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs).	49	9
10. Limited parental involvement and communication regarding the needs, progress and challenges of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs).	55	6.5

The findings suggest the need for targeted interventions in curriculum adaptation, teacher training, and resource allocation to address the most critical challenges. Professional development programs should prioritize equipping teachers with skills to customize lessons for SEN learners. The findings were corroborated by Francisco et al. (2020), who emphasize the importance of providing adequate training and resources to educators to ensure effective inclusion practices. Their study supports the findings that insufficient teacher preparation and limited teaching materials hinder the successful implementation of inclusive curricula. Similarly, Khotimah and Sutarto (2020) conform to these findings by highlighting the difficulties faced in adapting curricula to diverse learner needs, particularly in resource-constrained environments. Additionally, the lower prioritization of policy issues and teacher-pupil ratios mirrors findings from Boyle and Anderson (2020), who argue that while policies are essential, the practical execution of localized curricula often requires more immediate attention to classroom-level challenges.

Proposed Intervention to Increase the Level of Engagement of Learners. The proposed intervention, which is a training proposal entitled: FOR ALL (Facilitating Opportunities and Resources for Accessible Localized Learning): A Workshop Series and Materials Localization for Inclusive Education, addresses the identified engagement challenges in the research findings. The proposal aimed at enhancing the implementation of inclusive education in elementary schools. The program seeks to address persistent challenges in inclusive education, such as fostering peer interaction, adapting the curriculum, integrating technology tools, and providing teachers with adequate training. Recognizing the need for localized educational materials, the training will equip teachers with the necessary skills to develop culturally relevant resources that cater to Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs). Anchored in the 1987 Philippine Constitution and Republic Act No. 11650, which emphasize the right to quality education and inclusive learning for all, the seminar-workshop aims to empower educators through professional development.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from the study's findings are as follows:

1. Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) show high engagement in the localized curriculum in terms of its content, teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, and localized learning materials. This suggests that curriculum designers may continue to prioritize individualized and engaging content to maintain and enhance learner interest.
2. The components of the localized curriculum contributing significantly to learner engagement include curriculum adaptation and flexibility, quality and diverse teachers, policies and practices, a safe and supportive environment, and assessment and feedback. This implies that a holistic approach to curriculum design that integrates these components will be essential for fostering sustained engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).

3. There is a significant relationship between the localized curriculum along content of the localized curriculum, teaching and learning activities, assessment tasks, and localized learning materials and learners' levels of engagement particularly in curriculum adaptation and flexibility, as well as the quality of diverse teachers. This highlights the importance of training teachers in inclusive practices and ensuring curriculum adaptability to maximize engagement among Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).

4. The most pressing challenge in implementing the localized curriculum in the Inclusive Education Program is the difficulty in adapting the curriculum to address the diverse needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs), followed by creating a supportive learning environment and addressing gaps in teacher training, assessment tools, and localized teaching materials. This implies the need for a comprehensive approach to address these challenges, including targeted teacher training, resource allocation, and ongoing curriculum development to ensure inclusivity and engagement.

5. The training proposal as the study's intervention may provide teachers with practical skills, effective tools, and flexible resources that enhance their ability to engage students, fostering a more inclusive, accessible, and meaningful educational experience for all learners.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Curriculum designers may explore innovative strategies and resources that further personalize content to enhance learner engagement and interest for Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).
2. School heads may integrate professional development programs focusing on curriculum adaptation and flexibility, quality and diverse teachers, policies, and practices, a safe and supportive environment, and assessment and feedback to create a more cohesive curriculum that addresses the diverse needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).
3. Schools may offer ongoing training sessions for teachers on inclusive teaching practices and adaptive curriculum strategies to enhance their effectiveness in engaging Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs).
4. School heads may invest in additional resources, such as specialized materials and support personnel, to help educators effectively meet the unique needs of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) in the localized curriculum.
5. Schools may conduct the proposed training to strengthen teachers' skills in engaging SEN learners and adapting curriculum content to meet diverse needs.

The seminar-workshop series, designed for educators in inclusive education, may also be used by schools to address gaps in teacher preparedness and promote the development of culturally relevant, localized learning materials.

6. Future researchers may examine the long-term impact of the localized curriculum on the academic performance and social development of Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSEs) and explore innovative tools and strategies to enhance its implementation in inclusive education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers sought permission from the respondents to survey with an informed consent form. The respondents' information was kept confidential. Before the tabulation of data, each name was replaced with a respondent number to maintain anonymity. Moreover, the research upholds gender and cultural sensitivity, treating all participants with the utmost respect of their diverse perspectives.

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